

Monastery of Saint John the Theologian, Patmos

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Greece, Religious Group, Monastery, Greek Orthodox, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Aegean, Christian Traditions, Orthodox Christianity, Dodecanese, Religious Place, Orthodoxy

Patmos, the Greek island of the Dodecanese is reputed the place where Saint John the Apostle (also known as Saint John the Theologian) wrote the Book of Revelation (Apocalypse), and according to the tradition, the Fourth Gospel. Following the donation of the island in 1088 to Hosios Christodoulos of Mount Latros, as well as privileges granted by emperor Alexios I Komnenos, a Monastery dedicated to the “beloved disciple” of Christ was founded on the island. The Monastery which is surrounded by high defensive walls is located on a mountain peak above the island’s main harbour. Despite the fact that Patmos until then was uninhabited and waterless, the construction of the fortified complex began immediately after the settlement of the monks. The earliest structures of the Monastery are the domed cross-in-square katholikon (main church) and the Refectory, both integrating early-Christian spolia. The Monastery, which became a popular pilgrimage in the 12th century due to the growing fame of Saint Christodoulos’s relics began to flourish during this period. It also became connected to larger metropolitan centres. This is witnessed by the sophistication of the iconographic program and the style of the monumental decoration of the refectory and the chapel dedicated to Leontios, built in ca. 1185. It was also during the same period that the Refectory was vaulted and repainted, and the esonarthex of the katholikon was built. The exonarthex and the tomb chapel of Saint Christodoulos were also probably built during this period. The two-storeyed arcade on the south side was built in 1698. The cave located approximately halfway between the main port of Patmos and the old settlement (Chora), is the Cave of the Apocalypse (Spilaion tis Apokalypseos in Greek), where according to tradition Saint John dictated the Book of Revelation and his Gospel to Prochoros, his disciple. The cave emerged later also as a focus of pilgrimage. The fresco in the cave depicting John dictating to Prochoros dates from the late 12th century. The Monastery possesses rich archives dating back to the 11th century, while it holds an important collection of manuscripts, metalwork objects, liturgical vestments and icons. Apparently the Monastery owned also its own scriptorium. The historic centre of the island of Patmos, including the old settlement of Chora, the Monastery of Saint John the Theologian and the Cave of the Apocalypse was inscribed on the List of UNESCO World Heritage Sites in 1999.

Date Range: 1088 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Patmos, Dodecanese

Region tags: Greece, Aegean, Dodecanese, Patmos

Monastery of Saint John the Theologian and Cave of the Apocalypse

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

- ↳ Type of elevation
 - Hill

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In modernity
– Renaissance
– Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– No
Notes: The Monastery is dedicated to Saint John the Theologian.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: S. Papadopoulos, *The Monastery of Saint John the Theologian, Patmos*, 1987
- Source 2: A. Orlandos, *I Architektoniki kai ai byzantinai toichografiai tes Monis tou Theologou Patmou*, Athens, 1970
- Source 3: A. Komines (ed.), *Patmos, Treasures of the Monastery*, Athens 1988

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/942/>

– Source 1 Description: UNESCO List of World Heritage Monuments, "The Historic Centre (Chorá) with the Monastery of Saint-John the Theologian and the Cave of the Apocalypse on the Island of Pátmos"

– Source 1 URL: <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/patmos-monastery>

– Source 1 Description: Patmos Monastery on Google Arts and Culture

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was founded by Saint Christodoulos of Mount Latros, on the island of Patmos donated by emperor Alexios I Komnenos.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: Orthodox Monks

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built on the island where the Apocalypse was written and was dedicated to its author, Saint John the Theologian.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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- Source 1: S. Papadopoulos, *The Monastery of Saint John the Theologian*, Patmos, 1987
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- Source 1 URL: <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/patmos-monastery>
- Source 1 Description: Patmos Monastery on Google Arts and Culture

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

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↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

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– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is dedicated to Saint John the Theologian.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

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↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was founded by Saint Christodoulos of Mount Latros, on the island of Patmos donated by emperor Alexios I Komnenos.

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↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built on the island where the Apocalypse was written and was dedicated to its author, Saint John the Theologian.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Iconostasis and icons.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction,

etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Apostles, Virgin Mary.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The animals depicted are part of the narrative scenes of the monumental cycle of the katholikon.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: The decoration of the bema cannot be seen due to the presence of the iconostasis.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

Notes: There is need for autopsy in order to know which was the technique used for the wall paintings.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and the Saints.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a modern mosaic above the entrance of the cave of the Apocalypse.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Notes: A modern mosaic exists above the entrance of the cave of the Apocalypse.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: They provide information regarding the person and the event depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions are always accompanying scenes and portraits in Byzantine art.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Hill

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels and demons

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Last Judgement

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Miracles and events from the life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The monumental cycle of the katholikon of the Monastery includes narrative scenes and the depiction of Saints, Prophets, Christ, the Virgin.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Pigments and binders were used for the frescoes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Hill

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

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– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
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↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
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– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Pigments and binders were used for the frescoes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Iconostasis and icons.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Apostles, Virgin Mary.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The animals depicted are part of the narrative scenes of the monumental cycle of the katholikon.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: The decoration of the bema cannot be seen due to the presence of the iconostasis.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

Notes: There is need for autopsy in order to know which was the technique used for the wall paintings.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, the Virgin and the Saints.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a modern mosaic above the entrance of the cave of the Apocalypse.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Notes: A modern mosaic exists above the entrance of the cave of the Apocalypse.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: They provide information regarding the person and the event depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions are always accompanying scenes and portraits in Byzantine art.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels and demons

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Last Judgement

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Miracles and events from the life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The monumental cycle of the katholikon of the Monastery includes narrative scenes and the depiction of Saints, Prophets, Christ, the Virgin.

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

|

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Liturgies, Services, Commemorations, including the feast of Saint John the Theologian, to which the Monastery is dedicated, as well as that of Saint Christodoulos of Patmos, its founder.;

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Couple of times per year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox Typikon is followed

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox Typikon is followed

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Liturgies, Services, Commemorations.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes pilgrims and donors offer valuable objects.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrims and donors can offer to the monastery whatever they want, including daily-life objects

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Pilgrims and donors can offer whatever they want, from food, drinks to extremely expensive artefacts or money.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery has different phases.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: By the monastic community in collaboration with the Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese, belonging to the Greek Ministry of Culture.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: A group of experts is overlooking the monument and its conservation.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Liturgies, Services, Commemorations, including the feast of Saint John the Theologian, to which the Monastery is dedicated, as well as that of Saint Christodoulos of Patmos, its founder.;

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Couple of times per year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox Typikon is followed

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox Typikon is followed

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Liturgies, Services, Commemorations.

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes pilgrims and donors offer valuable objects.

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrims and donors can offer to the monastery whatever they want, including daily-life objects

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Other

– Other [specify]: Pilgrims and donors can offer whatever they want, from food, drinks to

extremely expensive artefacts or money.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery has different phases.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: By the monastic community in collaboration with the Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese, belonging to the Greek Ministry of Culture.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: A group of experts is overlooking the monument and its conservation.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The monastery owns an important collection of manuscripts and archival records dating from the 11th century onwards

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: This is a male monastic community

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The head of the Monastery is the abbot

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible though that throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Notes: Throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Notes: Throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: Throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The whole island was donated to the Monastery, so important part of the resources may well have been sold or distributed by the community

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Apocalypse and possibly the Fourth Gospel were written on the island of Patmos

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Following the donation of the island in 1088 to Hosios Christodoulos of Mount Latros, as well as privileges granted by emperor Alexios I Komnenos, a Monastery dedicated to the “beloved disciple” of Christ was founded on the island

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and hieromonks

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The whole island of Patmos was donated to the Monastery by emperor Alexios I Komnenos. Its is therefore normal that the most important resources of the island still belong to the Monastery

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The monastic community and the Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese that belongs to the Greek Ministry of Culture

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: This is a male monastic community

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The head of the Monastery is the abbot

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The monastic community and the Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese that belongs to the Greek Ministry of Culture

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The whole island of Patmos was donated to the Monastery by emperor Alexios I Komnenos. Its is therefore normal that the most important resources of the island still belong to the Monastery

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible though that throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Notes: Throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Notes: Throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: Throughout its history, the Monastery has played this role

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The whole island was donated to the Monastery, so important part of the resources may well have been sold or distributed by the community

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The monastery owns an important collection of manuscripts and archival records dating from the 11th century onwards

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

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↳ Are they written:

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↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and hieromonks

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

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